

THE OVERVIEW OF APPLYING REFLECTIVE WRITING IN ELT IN UZBEKISTAN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Teaching writing skills in English Language Teaching (ELT) in tertiary education has been an interesting area to research due to the fact that writing as a subject has various genres to be taught, namely, essay, report, summary, reflection, etc. Most teacher-researchers have been concerned about selecting that writing genre which can bring real life context into the classroom and enhance students' employability skills. In this manner, reflective writing can provide unique way of teaching by combining several functions such as developing writing skills, improving critical thinking and reflective skills, connecting theory with practice, relating past, present and future learning experiences with one another.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” introduced on October 8, 2019 points out that local tertiary education is expected to alter from theory-based to practice oriented education (LEX. UZ online, 2019). It is resulted from analyzing the positive outcomes of foreign universities that have been adhering to this approach. The decree also mentions some present gaps existing in the educational system of Uzbekistan highlighting that most students do not possess competent critical thinking, independent library search and analytical thinking skills (LEX. UZ online, 2019). The decree envisions providing higher educational institutions with more independence to enable them to offer more individualized teaching approach, develop students' creative thinking and encourage learners immerse themselves in practice-based education. In addition, the document emphasizes the essentiality of designing higher education academic programs that are truly based on job market demand and students' interests (LEX. UZ online, 2019).

Indeed, the higher education system of Uzbekistan has been experiencing certain positive changes in the last years. Establishment of international, non-governmental and private universities has opened new prospects in the sphere of education. Currently, the total number of functioning higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan is 224 (Study in Uzbekistan, n.d.). Consequently, the field has been witnessing relatively fair competition among universities to offer quality education. Especially, the discipline of teaching English as a foreign language has gone through remarkable changes. Interaction based and learner centered teaching methodologies replaced traditional ways of teaching that were built on memorizing grammar rules, drilling and repetition (Sattar, 2023).

As one of the contemporary teaching methods, reflective learning is being applied in ELT classrooms. More often university instructors decide on teaching reflective writing in their Writing classes. Reflective writing has also been discussed in a number of local teacher-researchers` publications and used as a method to assess students` performance. Namely, Juraev (2022) while describing the goals of teaching in his work, mentions the function of reflection in education. As he explains, reflection in pedagogy implies understanding the actions of yours and others (colleagues, students), to help them and accommodate your actions to theirs.

Foreign educators and researchers have been exploring the concept of reflective learning in their studies highlighting the necessity for implementing reflection into everyday classes and assessment tasks. According to Megnafi (2021), if students are aware about how they learn, they can become efficient learners. With the help of reflection, students can be involved in effective and autonomous study. McGuire, et al. (2009) believe that to enable students to cope with existing challenges in their future working areas, teachers should apply suitable teaching methods that can provide necessary knowledge and skills (f). McGuire, et al. (2009) suggest that reflection can serve as an important skill to work in various practice-based situations. They think that by assigning reflection paper to students, teachers can promote self-reflection and critical thinking of learners. According to Fink (2003) as cited by McGuire et al. (2009), “Reflective writing ... focuses on the writer’s learning

experience itself and attempts to identify the significance and meaning of a given learning experience, primarily for the writer”. As McGuire et al. (2009) point out, term paper used to be the indicator to measure students` performance in tertiary education. Despite the fact that this type of task can present student`s knowledge in certain issue, it can limit learners with not enabling them to reflect deeper on their biases or show students` capability to implement that insight with certain usage in real context. Reflective writing in fact, can help learners to achieve self-reflection and smooth combination of theoretical and practical knowledge. At the same time, reflective writing can guide students to realize the relations of personal experiences with professional values (Walmsley and Birkbeck, 2006, as cited by McGuire et al., 2009). Megnafi (2021) explains that students can target reflection by observing their performance in the learning process, analyzing their actions that led to certain outcomes, making conclusions based on their gained experience and forecasting their future actions.

Reflective writing has some limitations that any educator should consider before using and minimize the risk of task failure in the classroom. One of the drawbacks of implementing reflective writing can be challenges in assessing and grading learners` reflection (UCD, n.d.). Therefore, teachers have to develop reliable and valid assessment criteria to evaluate reflections. Another disadvantage that reflection can lead to is violation of ethical norms within teacher-student relationship. In fact, students can disclose some personal and anonymous pieces of information to their peers and teacher, which can deteriorate issues of trust among them (UCD, n.d.). While reflection offers several advantages to the educators, it requires from them meaningful guidance and explicit explanations towards students. Due to the fact that most students in writing reflection end up with depicting their experiences excluding reflecting on the cases, teachers should guide learners to shift from description to analysis process (UTS, 2024). Another common mistake in learners` reflective writing is expressing indefinite, unclear and general views. For this reason, educators have to supervise learners to stay focused on described issue and reflect on concrete items. The next obstacle teachers may face while teaching reflection is “reflection

fatigue” disorder, when a number of subjects require learners to write reflections as the part of assessments (UTS, 2024). Overuse of reflection in the curriculum can make students feel boredom, tiredness and confusion. In addition to the mentioned disadvantages of reflection, some students may wrongly believe that they have to sound positive in their reflective writing. As a result, they can make false impressions on the reader by pretending that they have done everything right in particular case (UTS, 2024). Educators may have challenges not only in teaching reflective writing, but also in assessing it. For instance, while reading students` reflections, teachers may find it difficult to mark writings since students can choose different situations to reflect on. In this case, teachers are recommended to have clear task instructions to direct students to the expected outcome. Moreover, teachers are advised to treat reflection as more personal expression of the views rather than theoretical assessment of students` knowledge. Since reflective writing can affect both teacher and student and promote reciprocal relationship between them, this type of writing can be utilized for low-stakes assessment tasks to prevent violation of test validity and reliability (UTS, 2024).

In conclusion, implementing teaching reflective writing in ELT setting in Uzbekistan`s higher educational system can truly meet the requirements set by the local government in terms of creating practice-based education with the focus on developing students` critical thinking skills. Several researches made on reflective writing demonstrate that the current type of writing can help to shift from theory to practice, since learners reflect on real-life situations and analyze their personal experiences about those cases. Furthermore, integrating reflective writing into curriculum can guarantee upswing in students` critical thinking skills. This positive increase can be resulted from encouraging learners to make connections within their past, present and future experiences regarding certain real-life situations in teaching reflective writing. Meanwhile, reflective writing can seem as less preferable genre to be taught, due to some limitations like requiring constant and thorough guidance and explicit explanations of teachers, clear assessment instructions and reliable assessment criteria. Nevertheless, all of these should not discourage educators from

implementing reflective writing into their syllabi, because well-planned teaching and right usage of reflective learning can bring guaranteed benefits both for learners and teachers. Certainly, teaching reflective writing in ELT context in tertiary education is suggested to be researched more, so that unidentified benefits and possible limitations can be revealed and taken into consideration to achieve better results and efficiency.

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